

D.2.4.P5 Full-scale Pilot 5 - Preservation and access to records with geodata

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1. Executive Summary

This document is part of the deliverable:

D2.4) Pilot documentation

Pilot documentation: This package of documentation will provide technical and end-user guidance to support not only the pilot sites but also possible future deployments thereafter. [month 33] (from DoW)

Structure of this deliverable

The deliverable is a package of linked documents.

This **Summary** contains the common information and short overview of the pilots, along with links to the final version of the Pilot Definition excel files and Pilot Documentation Packages. The **Pilot Definition** excel provides detailed information about scenarios, data sets and step-by-step preparation and process step instructions. The **Pilot Documentation Package** is created by the pilot staff responsible for the pilot execution. This package contains additional information along with screenshots (and videos in some cases) of the tools during the execution of the pilot.

Summary (this document) – Created by WP2

Pilot Package – Pilot 1

- Pilot Definition (Final version) – Created by WP2 and Pilot 1 responsible
- Pilot Documentation files – Created by Pilot 1

Pilot Package – Pilot 2

- Pilot Definition (Final version) – Created by WP2 and Pilot 2 responsible
- Pilot Documentation files – Created by Pilot 2

Pilot Package – Pilot 3

- Pilot Definition (Final version) – Created by WP2 and Pilot 3 responsible
- Pilot Documentation files – Created by Pilot 3

Pilot Package – Pilot 4

- Pilot Definition (Final version) – Created by WP2 and Pilot 4 responsible
- Pilot Documentation files – Created by Pilot 4

Pilot Package – Pilot 5

- Pilot Definition (Final version) – Created by WP2 and Pilot 5 responsible
- Pilot Documentation files – Created by Pilot 5

Pilot Package – Pilot 6

- Pilot Definition (Final version) – Created by WP2 and Pilot 1 responsible
- Pilot Documentation files – Created by Pilot 6

Pilot Package – Pilot 7

- Pilot Definition (Final version) – Created by WP2 and Pilot 7 responsible
- Pilot Documentation files – Created by Pilot 7

2. Pilot documentation

2.1 Introduction

During the e-ARK project the standardized method for ingesting geo data was developed. This allows the archives to offer geodata as a selection and display criteria of records by means of integration of current state of the art tools.

The aim of the Pilot 5 is to test the use above mentioned method for ingesting geodata and providing access using E-ARK tools. Specifications define the structure and the formats for this data as well as the structure of documentation needed to reuse geodata in the future.

Geodata can be stored as unstructured data or as a database or as a combination of these two. Also for previewing and managing geodata special tools (GIS applications) are required. The aim of this pilot was to show that we can package geodata with all the needed contextual information and metadata in order to enable access in the future. For this pilot we only developed and tested the geodata in simple vector format. Definition of raster based geodata, complex vector geodata and other formats is out of scope of this project.

2.1.1 Organisations involved

We ingested geodata from two institutions using different systems in order to prove that the same guidelines and structure can be used with different producers and that we can use the same access tools in order to display geodata from both systems.

The organisations involved were The Surveying and Mapping authority of the Republic of Slovenia and the Slovenian Environment Agency as geodata producers and the Archives of the Republic of Slovenia as the archive.

This document represents the description of the execution of the Pilot 5 scenarios.

2.2 Software components.

The main software products used in this pilot are: Roda-In, ESS Arch tools (ETP, ETA, EPP), eark Web integrated platform, OMT (Order management tool), IP Viewer and QGIS.

2.2.1 Roda-In

RODA-in is a tool specially designed for producers and archivists to create Submission Information Packages (SIP) ready to be submitted to an Open Archival Information System (OAIS). The tool creates SIPs from files and folders available on the local file system. The tool supports the E-ARK IP Specification and EAD3 descriptive metadata. (<http://rodain.roda-community.org/>)

2.2.2 ESS Arch tools

ESSArch (<http://www.essolutions.se/ESSArch>) is based on OAIS (Open Archival Information System, ISO 14721:2003) and further on developed to include both PreIngest and PreAccess functions, Storage Methodes and flexibility to add any metadata standard required. ESS Arch is comprised of 3 main tools:

- **ETP (ESS Tools for producers)** – A linux based tool for Pre-Ingest. This tool enables the producer to create and submit Submission Information Packages (SIP) to the archive.
- **ETA (ESS Tools for Archivists)** – A linux based tool for Accepting the SIP's submitted using ETP or other tools for creating SIP packages according to E-ARK specification. This tool also provides some validation tools
- **EPP (ESS Preservation Platform)** – A linux based tool for Archival package management. It supports final validation of the SIP package, Creation and management of AIP's and more.

2.2.3 eark Web integrated platform

E-ARK Web (<https://github.com/eark-project/earkweb>) is an open source archiving and digital preservation system. It is OAIS-oriented which means that data ingest, archiving and dissemination functions operate on information packages bundling content and metadata in contiguous containers. The components we used in this pilot were:

- SIP2AIP – This tool was used to create search index entry based on EAD metadata in the SIP package
- AIP2DIP – This tool contains several functions supporting identification and delivery of requested AIPs (Archival Information Packages)
- Lily – search engine

2.2.4 OMT (Order Management Tool)

This tool, integrates the search and order management capability. It enables the end user to find and order the chosen archival records and enables the Archivist to receive, manage and deliver the order to the end user.

2.2.5 IP Viewer

This tool enables the end user to preview the contents of the received order of archival records, and preview the contextual and process metadata for the contents of the order.

2.2.6 QGIS

This is an opensource GIS tool, that can be used to preview, manage, edit and modify geodata. It is used by the archivist in the Ingest process for validating the content of geodata records and in the process of DIP preparation. The enduser can use this tool to preview and analyse the geodata received in his order. (<http://www.qgis.org/en/site/>).

2.3 Description of scenarios

This document is based on the objectives and scenarios that are described in the separate document: E-ARK - Pilot definition - Pilot 5 v2.xlsx

Scenario 1: SIP Creation and Ingest of records with Geodata (2 representations)

Scenario 2: Search and Access information using Geodata (2 representations)

Scenario 3: SIP Creation and Ingest of records with Geodata (1 representation)

Scenario 4: Search and Access information using Geodata (1 representation)

2.3.1 General workflow of pre-ingest and ingest scenarios (1,3)

- Preparation of Geodata according to guidelines (formats and folder structure)
- Creation of EAD metadata for the package

- Packaging of geodata and its documentation using a SIP creation tool (Roda-In or ESS ETP)
- Submission of the created SIP into ESS ETA tool (package validation and antivirus check)
- Other validation and modification of the SIP are done in the ESS EPP tool
- Ingesting of the SIP into ESS EPP tool > AIP is created

2.3.2 General workflow of access (Scenarios 2,4)

- Search Indexes are updated for the AIP package that was ingested
 - Search index is created in the E-ARK web (Lily and SOLR – SIP2AIP tool)
 - Geodata is used to update the index in Peripleo
- Search and records selection is performed in OMT and order is generated
- Order is processed and ordered AIPs are requested from the repository (E-ARK Web – AIP2DIP tool)
- Order is prepared (OMT)
 - Geodata is modified if necessary and compiled into a project in QGIS
 - Sensitive data are omitted if required
- User is notified
- User can preview the order in IP Viewer and In geodata browsers (QGIS, Geoserver)
- After use order is managed (deleted, updated...)

2.4 Preparation of GEO data

2.4.1 Files and folder ready for SIP

2.4.1.1 EAD catalogue data

The EAD3 (ead.xml) file that has to accompany the data in the SIP is prepared manually. During the project, the EAD editor has been prepared and it is used by the tester before preparing the SIP.

2.4.1.2 Scenario 1

In scenario 1, the SIP package will be created using Roda-In tool. Roda-In creates the folder structure according to E-ARK IP Specification, so it is better to prepare the files in a flat structure. Data will be organised within the Roda-In application.

Data Set 1, producer: GURS

2.4.1.3 Scenario 3

Data Set 2, producer: ARSO

s:\PROJEKTI_ARS\e-ARH.si\E-ARK\Izvajanje projekta\WP2\GeoPaketi\
ARSO_GeoIP

2.5 Scenario 1

2.5.1 Pre-ingest

- RODA-In

The procedure of SIP creation using Roda-In tool is displayed in the attached video

(Roda-In_SIP_Creation.mp4)

After that we submit the SIP package into the ESS Arch ETA tool.

2.5.2 Ingest

2.5.2.1 ESS Arch ETA

In the ETA tool we can preview the existing SIPs waiting to be received in the “Receive IP:” menu.

Select one (as submitted with ETP)

ETA ESSArch Tools for Archive
Welcome, admin @ zone2. Change password / Log out

RECEIVE ▾ EVENTS ▾ TRANSFER ▾ MANAGEMENT ▾ HELP ▾

Receive information packages

Opt	Archivist organization	Label	Create date	IP type	IP location	IP (UUID)	IP state
<input type="checkbox"/>	ARStest	IngestTestBoris	2016-09-22T10:30:31+02:00	SIP	/ESSArch/data/eta/reception/efr/ip9	UUID:7f356f48-809e-11e6-8531-005056982d8b	Not received
<input type="checkbox"/>	ARStest	BorisTest2	2016-09-22T10:52:46+02:00	SIP	/ESSArch/data/eta/reception/efr/ip10	UUID:166b2636-80a0-11e6-be53-005056982d8b	Not received
<input type="checkbox"/>	Agencija za Okolje RS	Natura2000_2004_Test05	2016-09-26T10:22:44+02:00	SIP	/ESSArch/data/eta/reception/efr/ip11	UUID:86d55242-83c1-11e6-a112-005056982d8b	Not received

Please specify validation requirements in connection with the reception of IP

Validate package specification file? Yes No

Validate content of package (IP)? Yes No

In this case we need to prepare a SIP to be ingested, since it was not created in the ETP tool, so it lacks the metadata needed for the ETA tool .

Prepare IP:

Arhivski Organizacija	<input type="text" value="RIS"/>
Arhivski Naziv	<input type="text" value="HR Employee"/>
Arhivski Naziv	<input type="text" value="ZSD"/>
Arhivski Naziv	<input type="text" value="Narodni"/>
Oznaka Organizacije	<input type="text" value="Government X, Dep V"/>
Prostora Organizacije	<input type="text" value="Government X, Central Dep"/>
Prostora Inhibitor	<input type="text" value="Govt Services"/>
Prostora Naziva	<input type="text" value="Government X, system line"/>
Razlike Organizacije	<input type="text" value="Government X, Service Dep"/>
Razlike Inhibitor	<input type="text" value="Life Net"/>
IP Oznaka Inhibitor	<input type="text" value="Government X, Legal Dep"/>
Prostora Inhibitor Organizacije	<input type="text" value="National Services of X"/>
Razlike Inhibitor Organizacije	<input type="text" value="NL 020110200 2010010"/>
Razlike Inhibitor	<input type="text" value="2010101"/>
Prostora Inhibitor	<input type="text" value="2010102"/>
Oznaka Naziva	<input type="text" value="Inherit"/>
Inhibitor	<input type="text"/>
Mati. Inhibitor	<input type="text" value="Inet"/>
Mati. Tip	<input type="text" value="SIP"/>
Mati. ID	<input type="text" value="8a223a20-0201-1a00-0a00-000000000000"/>
Mati. Oznaka	<input type="text" value="2010010201-1a00-0a00-000000000000"/>
Oznaka Naziva	<input type="text" value="2010102111 20110202"/>
Razlike Naziva	<input type="text" value="Inet"/>
<input type="button" value="Submit"/>	

Transfer IP:

The screenshot shows the top navigation bar of the ESSArch Tools for Archive interface. The 'TRANSFER' menu is selected. Below the navigation bar, the page title is 'Transfer information packages'. There are several filter tabs: 'Opt', 'Archivist organization', 'Label', 'Create date', 'IP type', 'IP location', 'IP (UUID)', and 'IP state'. A text field contains the instruction 'Transfer to local filesystem: /ESSArch/data/gate/reception'. At the bottom, there is a prominent 'Transfer IP' button.

At the end, Management status;

The screenshot shows the 'MANAGEMENT' section of the ESSArch Tools for Archive interface. The 'MANAGEMENT' menu item is circled in red. Below the navigation bar, there is a search bar and a table titled 'Select information package to change'. The table lists various information packages with columns for Archivist organization, Label, Createdate, Iptype, Uuid, Site profile, State, and Zone. A filter sidebar on the right allows filtering by organization, state, and zone.

Archivist organization	Label	Createdate	Iptype	Uuid	Site profile	State	Zone
GURS3	test1	2016-09-26T14:36:33+02:00	SIP	a2ce491e-a79e-40eb-b88b-8c600d227197	NO	Transmitted	zone2
ESS	test1	2016-09-26T14:15:05+02:00	SIP	d27ea7e8-7db0-4de9-84ca-634694061211	NO	Transmitted	zone2
ESS	test20160920_1	2016-09-20T16:28:53+02:00	SIP	2f7d646-7f3e-11e6-8531-005056982d8b	NO	Transmitted	zone2
ESS	test_20160916_1	2016-09-16T13:09:07+02:00	SIP	06e85bc4-7fb6-11e6-a189-005056982d8b	NO	Transmitted	zone2
ARSO	Natura 2000 - do 2014	2016-09-15T15:23:00+02:00	SIP	97c45e1c-7b39-11e6-baf8-005056982d8b	NO	Transmitted	zone2
GURS	GURS Občine Test 2SEP	2016-09-02T11:56:46+02:00	SIP	884d156a-70f2-11e6-8f37-005056982d8b	NO	Transmitted	zone2
MyOrgnaization	ARS	2016-08-31T11:42:20+02:00	SIP	2af8aae6-6f5e-11e6-94bb-005056982d8b	NO	Transmitted	zone2
ESS	test 1 160831	2016-08-31T11:23:28+02:00	SIP	301c47c-6f5c-11e6-a4c4-005056982d8b	NO	Transmitted	zone2
ESS	Test 2	2016-06-16T11:10:14+02:00	SIP	318ec66c-33a1-11e6-952b-005056982d8b	NO	Transmitted	zone2
ESS	Test 1	2016-06-09T16:53:58+02:00	SIP	ee9480a0-2e4f-11e6-bc2e-005056982d8b	NO	Transmitted	zone2

2.5.2.2 ESS Arch EPP

The screenshot shows the top navigation bar of the ESSArch Preservation Platform (EPP). The 'MANAGEMENT' menu is selected. The page title is 'EPP (ESSArch Preservation Platform)'. The navigation bar includes 'CONTROL AREA', 'INGEST', 'ACCESS', 'ADMINISTRATION', 'REPORTS', 'MANAGEMENT', and 'HELP'.

EPP (ESSArch Preservation Platform) 2.7.5 - Status at 2016-10-10 14:56

Processes:

- SIPReceiver: 1
- SIPValidateAIS: 1
- SIPValidateApproval: 1
- SIPValidateFormat: 1
- AIPCreator: 1
- AIPChecksum: 1
- AIPValidate: 1
- SIPRemove: 1
- AIPWriter: 1
- AIPPurge: 1
- TLD: 1
- db_sync_ais: 1
- ESSlogging: 1

Storage media overview

- Archive tapes online: None
- Add new tapes starting with: None
- Write tapes: None
- Empty tapes: None
- Error tapes: None
- Ongoing requests:

User	Request purpose	Status	Info
No uncompleted requests			

Execute the steps in the Control area to create the AIP:

The screenshot displays the EPP (ESSArch Preservation Platform) interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the title "EPP (ESSArch Preservation Platform)" and several menu items: "CONTROL AREA", "INGEST", "ACCESS", "ADMINISTRATION", "REPORTS", "MANAGEMENT", and "HELP". The "CONTROL AREA" menu is expanded, showing a list of actions: "CheckIn from Rece...", "CheckOut to Workarea", "CheckIn from Workarea", "CheckOut to Gatearea from work", "CheckIn from Gatearea to work", "CheckIn from Gatearea", "DiffCheck", "Preserve Information Package", "Delete IP in Controlarea", and "Overview of controlarea requests". A tooltip "Manage information packages etc ..." is visible over the first item. Below the menu, the main content area shows the title "Arch Preservation Platform) 2.7.5 - Sta" and a section titled "Storage mec". Under "Storage mec", there are several lines of text, some of which are redacted with green bars: "Archive tapes online", "None", "Add new tapes starti", "None", "Write tapes:", and "None".

2.6 Scenario 2

2.6.1 Access

2.6.1.1 Create Index in E-ARK Web and Peripleo

2.6.1.2 Search in the OMT Search or in Peripleo

The Peripleo configuration is still not finished

Search in Peripleo gives us a result

2.6.1.3 OMT and Order submission service

Example screenshots, since the tool is still under development

2.6.1.4 IP viewer

Tool is still under development – this are demo screenshots

Figure 8 – Screenshot of DIP Viewer

2.6.1.5 QGIS

Geodata can then be opened and previewed in QGIS

2.7 Scenario 3

2.7.1 Pre-ingest - ESS Arch ETP

2.7.1.1 Preparations

2.7.1.2 Creation of an empty EAD file

- Open java tool Folder_to_EAD3
- Select the input folder for scenario 3:

```
String topfolder = "s:/PROJEKTI_ARS/e-ARH.si/E-ARK/Izvajanje projekta/WP2/GeoPaketi/ARSO_GeoIP";
```

- Run the program

```
2016-10-18 10:56: Executing example.EADcreator:
```

```
EAD> EADcreator,
```

```
input folder: s:/PROJEKTI_ARS/e-ARH.si/E-ARK/Izvajanje projekta/WP2/GeoPaketi/ARSO_GeoIP
```

```
EAD> Prefix for DAO elements:
```

```
EAD> OUT s:\PROJEKTI_ARS\e-ARH.si\E-ARK\Izvajanje projekta\WP2\GeoPaketi\ARSO_GeoIP\documentation
```

```
EAD> OUT s:\PROJEKTI_ARS\e-ARH.si\E-ARK\Izvajanje projekta\WP2\GeoPaketi\ARSO_GeoIP\representations
EAD> Done. Output file: M:\tIDE\.tide_global\Folder_to_EAD3\src\ead.xml
```

d. Later below we will use the file ead.xml

2.7.1.3 ETP steps

First we prepare IP:

Select Prepare IP:

Prepare new information packages

Please fill in the fields or use prefilled data (* indicates mandatory field)

Provides functionality to prepare the physical and logical structure of the information package in order to be able to add content into it.

Archivist organization *	<input type="text" value="ARStest"/>
Archive label	<input type="text" value="BorisTest3"/>
Agent Profile	<input type="text" value="ARS"/>
Classification Profile	<input type="text" value="ARS-CLASS"/>
Data Selection Profile (CTS)	<input type="text" value="ARS Geodata V.01"/>
Import Profile	<input type="text" value="Import from ArcGIS"/>
Transfer Project Profile	<input type="text" value="Transfer project Type GEO"/>

Then we Create IP. First we select the IP that is being prepared:

ETP ESSArch Tools for Producer

INFORMATION PACKAGE ▾ SUBMIT ▾ MANAGEMENT ▾ HELP ▾

Select which information package to create

Archivist organization	Label	Create date	IP type	IP location	IP (UUID)	IP state	Events	Editor
Geodetska uprava RS	GURS	2016-07-27T13:53:02+02:00	SIP	/ESSArch/data/etp/prepare/ip1	ac385f8a-53f0-11e6-803a-005056982d8b	Prepared	***	Editor
ARSO	ARSO_Natura2000	2016-08-19T10:29:43+02:00	SIP	/ESSArch/data/etp/prepare/ip2	1485663e-65e7-11e6-b995-005056982d8b	Prepared	***	Editor
Geodetska uprava RS	GURS	2016-08-29T10:14:35+02:00	SIP	/ESSArch/data/etp/prepare/ip3	9f42a440-6dc0-11e6-8602-005056982d8b	Prepared	***	Editor
Gregor Test	Gregor TEST SIP	2016-08-31T11:59:58+02:00	SIP	/ESSArch/data/etp/prepare/ip4	acda27fc-6f61-11e6-94bb-005056982d8b	Prepared	***	Editor
ARStest	BorisTest3	2016-10-18T08:49:27+02:00	SIP	/ESSArch/data/etp/prepare/ip5	0352b7e4-94ff-11e6-af59-005056982d8b	Prepared	***	Editor

Now we click the Label in order to upload the folder and files

ETP ESSArch Tools for Producer Welcome, admin. Change password / Log out

INFORMATION PACKAGE ▾ SUBMIT ▾ MANAGEMENT ▾ HELP ▾

Create information package

Please fill in the fields or use prefilled data (* indicates mandatory field)

Provides functionality to add descriptive metadata for selected prepared information package and to add content. The information package is then created as a submission information package (SIP) and a submit description is created in order to facilitate the submission of the SIP.

Archive label:	BorisTest3
Content type *:	ERMS ▾
Submission agreement:	RA 13-2011/5329; 2012-04-12
Archivist organization *:	ARStest
Submitter organization *:	Government X, Service Dep
Preservation organization *:	National Archives of X

 Content

We should add file here, but we do it manually on the server.

First we select the last file:

WinSCP


```
$ pwd
/ESSArch/data/etp/prepare
```

Find the latest folder:

Name	Size	Changed	Rights	Owner
..		27.5.2016 16:14:07	rw-rw-r-x	arch
ip5		<u>18.10.2016 8:49:27</u>	rw-rw-r-x	arch
ip4		31.8.2016 11:59:58	rw-rw-r-x	arch
ip3		29.8.2016 10:14:35	rw-rw-r-x	arch
ip2		19.8.2016 10:29:43	rw-rw-r-x	arch
ip1		27.7.2016 13:53:02	rw-rw-r-x	arch

Open it:

Name	Size	Changed	Rights	Owner
..		18.10.2016 8:49:27	rw-rw-r-x	arch
schemas		18.10.2016 8:49:27	rw-rw-r-x	arch
representations		18.10.2016 8:49:27	rw-rw-r-x	arch
metadata		18.10.2016 8:49:27	rw-rw-r-x	arch
documentation		18.10.2016 8:49:27	rw-rw-r-x	arch
log.xml	5 KB	18.10.2016 8:49:27	rw-r--r--	arch

Now copy the files:

```
Input documentation/*           → documentation
Input representations/rep1, rep2 → representations/rep1, rep2
Input ead.xml                   → metadata/descriptive/ead.xml
```

Name	Size	Changed	Rights	Owner
..		18.10.2016 9:04:16	rw-rw-r-x	arch
ead.xml	6 KB	18.10.2016 9:07:38	rw-rw-r--	arch

Now we check the package again : create SIP and Select Label:

ETP ESSArch Tools for Producer Welcome, admin. Change password / Log out

INFORMATION PACKAGE ▾ SUBMIT ▾ MANAGEMENT ▾ HELP ▾

Create information package

Please fill in the fields or use prefilled data (* indicates mandatory field)

Provides functionality to add descriptive metadata for selected prepared information package and to add content. The information package is then created as a submission information package (SIP) and a submit description is created in order to facilitate the submission of the SIP.

Archive label:	BorisTest3
Content type *:	ERMS ▾
Submission agreement:	RA 13-2011/5329; 2012-04-12
Archivist organization *:	ARStest
Submitter organization *:	Government X, Service Dep
Preservation organization *:	National Archives of X

Now we enter the EAD editor to complete the descriptions:

ETP ESSArch Tools for Producer Welcome, admin. Change password / Log out

INFORMATION PACKAGE ▾ SUBMIT ▾ MANAGEMENT ▾ HELP ▾

Select which information package to create

Archivist organization	Label	Create date	IP type	IP location	IP (UUID)	IP state	Events	Editor
Geodetska uprava RS	GURS	2016-07-27T13:53:02+02:00	SIP	/ESSArch/data/etp/prepare/ip1	ac385f8a-53f0-11e6-803a-005056982d8b	Prepared	***	Editor
ARSO	ARSO_Natura2000	2016-08-19T10:29:43+02:00	SIP	/ESSArch/data/etp/prepare/ip2	1485663e-65e7-11e6-b995-005056982d8b	Prepared	***	Editor
Geodetska uprava RS	GURS	2016-08-29T10:14:35+02:00	SIP	/ESSArch/data/etp/prepare/ip3	9f42a440-6dc0-11e6-8602-005056982d8b	Prepared	***	Editor
Gregor Test	Gregor TEST SIP	2016-08-31T11:59:58+02:00	SIP	/ESSArch/data/etp/prepare/ip4	acda27fc-6f61-11e6-94bb-005056982d8b	Prepared	***	Editor
ARStest	BorisTest4	2016-10-18T09:24:21+02:00	SIP	/ESSArch/data/etp/prepare/ip5	e3771ff0-9503-11e6-b638-005056982d8b	Prepared	***	Editor

https://etp.ars.sigov.si/static/eadead/filledForm.html?id=18

The EAD3 GEO Form

Select schema: **EAD3 GEO** Select language: **English**

ead

Control

Record Identifier:

File Description

Title Statement

Add Title Proper of the Finding Aid

Title Proper of the Finding Aid:

Maintenance Status: Value: **new**

...

...

Component

Level: **file**

Descriptive Identification

ID of the Unit:

Title of the Unit:

Digital Archival Object Set **X**

Label: **Digital Objects** Coverage: **part** Add Digital Archival Object

Link Title	Natura2K_2004_poizve	Hypertext Reference	documentation/Commo	Identifier	2fd3f16f-f9bf-4832-90fe	Digital Archival Object Type	derived	Coverage	part
X Link Title	Natura2K_2004_Strukt	Hypertext Reference	documentation/Logical s	Identifier	354e936d-aa49-4d39-a6	Digital Archival Object Type	derived	Coverage	part
X Link Title	NATURA2K_2004_ISC	Hypertext Reference	documentation/Metadat	Identifier	e4d327fa-dd5d-4276-9fi	Digital Archival Object Type	derived	Coverage	part
X Link Title	E_Brosura_N2000_LIFI	Hypertext Reference	documentation/Other dc	Identifier	a00f1d25-3ec8-4a33-9bi	Digital Archival Object Type	derived	Coverage	part
X Link Title	NATURA_SLO_2008.p	Hypertext Reference	documentation/Other dc	Identifier	406a7364-1db7-4181-88	Digital Archival Object Type	derived	Coverage	part
X Link Title	Toman_Proteus_septen	Hypertext Reference	documentation/Other dc	Identifier	eceda955-9fba-42da-82	Digital Archival Object Type	derived	Coverage	part
X Link Title	Natura2K_2004_kartog	Hypertext Reference	documentation/Visualis	Identifier	368de850-b1e8-4349-a6	Digital Archival Object Type	derived	Coverage	part

Add Component

Component **X**

We select Create and our package disappears from this list:

ETP ESSArch Tools for Producer Welcome, admin. Change password / Log out

INFORMATION PACKAGE SUBMIT MANAGEMENT HELP

Select which information package to create

Archivist organization	Label	Create date	IP type	IP location	IP (UUID)	IP state	Events	Editor
Geodetska uprava RS	GURS	2016-07-27T13:53:02+02:00	SIP	/ESSArch/data/etp/prepare/ip1	ac385f8a-53f0-11e6-803a-005056982d8b	Prepared	***	Editor
ARSO	ARSO_Natura2000	2016-08-19T10:29:43+02:00	SIP	/ESSArch/data/etp/prepare/ip2	1485663e-65e7-11e6-b995-005056982d8b	Prepared	***	Editor
Geodetska uprava RS	GURS	2016-08-29T10:14:35+02:00	SIP	/ESSArch/data/etp/prepare/ip3	9f42a440-6dc0-11e6-8602-005056982d8b	Prepared	***	Editor
Gregor Test	Gregor TEST	2016-08-31T11:59:58+02:00	SIP	/ESSArch/data/etp/prepare/ip4	acda27fc-6f61-11e6-94bb-005056982d8b	Prepared	***	Editor

X **X**

Now we can submit the package as it appears on the list for Submit

ETP ESSArch Tools for Producer

INFORMATION PACKAGE ▾ SUBMIT ▾ MANAGEMENT ▾ HELP ▾

Select which information package to submit

Archivist organization	Label	Create date	IP type	IP location	IP (UUID)	IP state
Arhiv Republike Slovenije	ARS	2016-08-02T10:34:55+02:00	SIP	/ESSArch/data/etp/reception/ip3	fd5ded04-588b-11e6-b006-005056982d8b	Created
ARStest	<u>BorisTest3</u>	2016-10-18T08:49:27+02:00	SIP	/ESSArch/data/etp/reception/ip13	0352b7e4-94ff-11e6-af59-005056982d8b	Created

ETP ESSArch Tools for Producer Welcome, admin. Change password / Log out

INFORMATION PACKAGE ▾ SUBMIT ▾ MANAGEMENT ▾ HELP ▾

Submit information package (*BorisTest3*) from (*ARStest*)

Please fill in the fields or use prefilled data (* indicates mandatory field)

Provides functionality for submitting the submission information package (SIP) and if required to send the submit description to intended receiver at the archivist organization.

The receiver of the IP

Receiver - Local filesystem: /ESSArch/data/eta/reception/etf

The receiver of the submit description

From: admin@essolutions.se

To *:

Subject *:

Body *:

We can also check the Management tab:

ETP ESSArch Tools for Producer Welcome, admin. Change password / Log out

INFORMATION PACKAGE | SUBMIT | **MANAGEMENT** | HELP

Home > ip > Information packages

Select information package to change

Search: Search

Action: Go 0 of 16 selected

<input type="checkbox"/>	Archivist organization	Label	Createdate	Iptype	Uuid	Site profile	State	Zone
<input type="checkbox"/>	Agencija za Okolje RS	Natura2000_2004_Test05	2016-09-26T10:16:29+02:00	SIP	86d55242-83c1-11e6-a112-005056982d8b	NO	Submitted	zone1
<input type="checkbox"/>	ARStest	BorisTest2	2016-09-22T10:39:34+02:00	SIP	166b2636-80a0-11e6-be53-005056982d8b	NO	Submitted	zone1
<input type="checkbox"/>	ARStest	IngestTestBoris	2016-09-22T10:28:10+02:00	SIP	7f356f48-809e-11e6-8531-005056982d8b	NO	Submitted	zone1
<input type="checkbox"/>	ESS	test20160920_1	2016-09-20T16:26:14+02:00	SIP	2f77d646-7f3e-11e6-8531-005056982d8b	NO	Submitted	zone1
<input type="checkbox"/>	ESS	test_20160916_1	2016-09-16T12:47:56+02:00	SIP	06e85bc4-7bfb-11e6-a189-005056982d8b	NO	Submitted	zone1
<input type="checkbox"/>	ARSO	Natura 2000 - do 2014	2016-09-15T13:43:17+02:00	SIP	97c45e1c-7b39-11e6-baf8-005056982d8b	NO	Submitted	zone1
<input type="checkbox"/>	GURS	GURS Občine Test 2SEP	2016-09-02T11:49:25+02:00	SIP	884d156a-70f2-11e6-8f37-005056982d8b	NO	Submitted	zone1
<input type="checkbox"/>	Gregor Test	Gregor TEST SIP	2016-08-31T11:59:58+02:00	SIP	acda27fc-6f61-11e6-94bb-005056982d8b	NO	Prepared	zone1
<input type="checkbox"/>	MyOrgnaization	ARS	2016-08-31T11:34:51+02:00	SIP	2af8eae6-6f5e-11e6-94bb-005056982d8b	NO	Submitted	zone1
<input type="checkbox"/>	ESS	test 1 160831	2016-08-31T11:20:41+02:00	SIP	301c47c-6f5c-11e6-a4c4-005056982d8b	NO	Submitted	zone1
<input type="checkbox"/>	Geodetska uprava RS	GURS	2016-08-29T10:14:35+02:00	SIP	9f42a440-6dc0-11e6-8602-005056982d8b	NO	Prepared	zone1
<input type="checkbox"/>	ARSO	ARSO_Natura2000	2016-08-19T10:29:43+02:00	SIP	1485663e-65e7-11e6-b995-005056982d8b	NO	Prepared	zone1
<input type="checkbox"/>	Arhiv Republike Slovenije	ARS	2016-08-02T10:34:55+02:00	SIP	fd5ded04-588b-11e6-b006-005056982d8b	NO	Created	zone1
<input type="checkbox"/>	Geodetska uprava RS	GURS	2016-07-27T13:53:02+02:00	SIP	ac385f8a-53f0-11e6-803a-005056982d8b	NO	Prepared	zone1
<input type="checkbox"/>	ESS	Test 2	2016-06-16T11:03:29+02:00	SIP	318ec66c-33a1-11e6-952b-005056982d8b	NO	Submitted	zone1
<input type="checkbox"/>	ESS	Test 1	2016-06-09T16:39:12+02:00	SIP	ee9480a0-2e4f-11e6-bc2e-005056982d8b	NO	Submitted	zone1

16 information packages

2.7.2 Ingest - ESS Arch ETA

When the package has been submitted, we can see it with archivists tool – ETA.

First we Receive IP:

ETA ESSArch Tools for Archive

RECEIVE | EVENTS | TRANSFER | MANAGEMENT | HELP

Receive IP

Prepare UIP

ETA ESSArch Tools for Archive Welcome, admin @ zone2. Change password / Log out

RECEIVE | EVENTS | TRANSFER | MANAGEMENT | HELP

Receive information packages

Opt	Archivist organization	Label	Create date	IP type	IP location	IP (UUID)	IP state
<input type="checkbox"/>	ARStest	IngestTestBoris	2016-09-22T10:30:31+02:00	SIP	/ESSArch/data/eta/reception/eft/ip9	UUID:7f356f48-809e-11e6-8531-005056982d8b	Not received
<input type="checkbox"/>	ARStest	BorisTest2	2016-09-22T10:52:46+02:00	SIP	/ESSArch/data/eta/reception/eft/ip10	UUID:166b2636-80a0-11e6-be53-005056982d8b	Not received
<input type="checkbox"/>	Agencija za Okolje RS	Natura2000_2004_Test05	2016-09-26T10:22:44+02:00	SIP	/ESSArch/data/eta/reception/eft/ip11	UUID:86d55242-83c1-11e6-a112-005056982d8b	Not received
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	ARStest	BorisTest3	2016-10-18T09:22:07+02:00	SIP	/ESSArch/data/eta/reception/eft/ip12	UUID:0352b7e4-94ff-11e6-af59-005056982d8b	Not received

Please specify validation requirements in connection with the reception of IP

Validate package specification file? Yes No

Validate content of package (IP)? Yes No

Receive IP

On the next screen we are immediately asked to review the logs:

The screenshot shows the top navigation bar of the ESSArch Tools for Archive interface. Below the navigation bar, there is a section titled "View log and add logevents". A table displays log entries with the following data:

Archivist organization	Label	Create date	IP type	IP location	IP (UUID)	IP state
ARStest	BorisTest3	2016-10-18T09:50:45+02:00	SIP	/ESSArch/data/eta/reception/ef	0352b7e4-94ff-11e6-af59-005056982d8b	Received

We click the Label. We can add a new event and see all the others as well:

The screenshot shows the "Add new event for (BorisTest3) from (ARStest)" form. The form includes a dropdown menu for "Event" set to "Delivery received", a dropdown menu for "Status" set to "Ok", and a text area for "Comments". Below the form is a button labeled "Add log event".

Below the form, the text "Log content" is circled in red. Below this, a table displays log entries with the following data:

Time	Type	Event	Status	Comments	Agent
2016-10-18T09:50:45+02:00	20000	Created log circular	Ok	Success to create logfile	admin

Now we continue with Prepare IP:

Arohivist Organization

Arohivist Software

Arohivist Software

Arohivist Software

Creator Organization

Producer Organization

Producer Individual

Producer Software

Submitter Organization

Submitter Individual

IPOwner Individual

Preservation Organization

... and select Submit.

ETA supports adding events also nothing new is in the event:

ETA **ESSArch Tools for Archive**

RECEIVE ▾ EVENTS ▾ TRANSFER ▾ MANAGEMENT ▾ HELP ▾

Add new event for (*BorisTest3*) from (*ARStest*)

Event: ▾

Status: ▾

Comments:

Log content

Time	Type	Event	Status	Comments	Agent
2016-10-18T09:50:45+02:00	20000	Created log circular	Ok	Success to create logfile	admin

We continue with Transfer IP:

ETA ESSArch Tools for Archive Welcome, admin @ ...

RECEIVE ▾ EVENTS ▾ TRANSFER ▾ MANAGEMENT ▾ HELP ▾

Transfer information packages

Opt	Archivist organization	Label	Create date	IP type	IP location	IP (UUID)	IP state
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	ARStest	BorisTest3	2016-10-18T09:22:07+02:00	SIP	/ESSArch/data/eta/reception/eft/ip12	UUID:0352b7e4-94ff-11e6-af59-005056982d8b	Received

Transfer to local filesystem: /ESSArch/data/gate/reception

[Transfer IP](#)

And the IP disappears:

ETA ESSArch Tools for Archive

RECEIVE ▾ EVENTS ▾ TRANSFER ▾ MANAGEMENT ▾ HELP ▾

Transfer information packages

Opt Archivist organization Label Create date IP type IP location IP (UUID) IP state

Transfer to local filesystem: /ESSArch/data/gate/reception

[Transfer IP](#)

We can review the package in the Information packages list:

ETA ESSArch Tools for Archive Welcome, admin @ ...

RECEIVE ▾ EVENTS ▾ TRANSFER ▾ MANAGEMENT ▾ HELP ▾

Home > Ip > Information packages

Information Packages
Administrare ESSArch Tools etc ..

Configuration

Select information package

Search

Action: ----- Go 0 of 11 selected

<input type="checkbox"/>	Archivist organization	Label	Createdate	Iptype	Uuid	Site profile	State	Zone
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	ARStest	BorisTest3	2016-10-18T09:50:45+02:00	SIP	0352b7e4-94ff-11e6-af59-005056982d8b	NO	Transmitted	zone2

Select column Archivist organization and we get

ETA ESSArch Tools for Archive Welcome, admin @ ... Change password / Log out

RECEIVE ▾ EVENTS ▾ TRANSFER ▾ MANAGEMENT ▾ HELP ▾

Home > Ip > Information packages > InformationPackage object

Change information package

History

Archivist organization:

Label:

Createdate:

Iptype:

Uuid:

Directory:

Site profile:

State:

Zone:

Progress:

[Delete](#) [Save and add another](#) [Save and continue editing](#) [Save](#)

2.7.3 Storage - ESS Arch EPP

The IP has been transferred with ETA. It is not immediately visible in EPP:

EPP (ESSArch Preservation Platform) Welcome, admin. Change password / L

CONTROL AREA ▾ INGEST ▾ ACCESS ▾ ADMINISTRATION ▾ REPORTS ▾ MANAGEMENT ▾ HELP ▾

ACCESS - List information packages

Show entries Column visibility Search:

Identification	Archivist organization	Label	Create date	Start date	End date	Type	Generation	State	Activity
fe9fbb70-2e51-11e6-acc0-005056982d8b	ESS	Test 1	2016-06-09	2011-12-31	2012-12-29	AIC			
22a0f624-33a2-11e6-9f40-005056982d8b	ESS	Test 2	2016-06-16	2016-04-11	2016-04-11	AIC			
8e9561a2-7f3e-11e6-badd-005056982d8b	ESS	test20160920_1	2016-09-20	2016-04-11	2016-04-11	AIC			

Showing 1 to 3 of 3 entries Previous 1 Next

These are the steps we will do:

EPP (ESSArch Preservation Platform) Welcome, admin. Char

CONTROL AREA ▾ INGEST ▾ ACCESS ▾ ADMINISTRATION ▾ REPORTS ▾ MANAGEMENT ▾ HELP ▾

Manage information packages etc ..

ACCESS - List information packages

Show entries Column visibility Search:

Identification	Archivist organization	Label	Create date	Start date	End date	Type	Generation	State	Activity
fe9fbb70-2e51-11e6-acc0-005056982d8b	ESS	Test 1	2016-06-09	2011-12-31	2012-12-29	AIC			
22a0f624-33a2-11e6-9f40-005056982d8b	ESS	Test 2	2016-06-16	2016-04-11	2016-04-11	AIC			
8e9561a2-7f3e-11e6-badd-005056982d8b	ESS	test20160920_1	2016-09-20	2016-04-11	2016-04-11	AIC			

Showing 1 to 3 of 3 entries Previous 1 Next

CONTROL AREA -> CheckIn from Reception

EPP (ESSArch Preservation Platform) Welcome, admin. Change

CONTROL AREA ▾ INGEST ▾ ACCESS ▾ ADMINISTRATION ▾ REPORTS ▾ MANAGEMENT ▾ HELP ▾

Select which information package to checkin from reception

Show entries Column visibility Search:

Identification	Archivist organization	Label	Create date	Start date	End date	Type	Media	State
0352b7e4-94ff-11e6-af59-005056982d8b	ARStest	BorisTest3	2016-10-18T09:22:07+02:00	2016-04-12	2016-04-12	SIP	EFT	Reception

Showing 1 to 1 of 1 entries (filtered from 9 total entries) Previous **1** Next

We click on Identification:

EPP (ESSArch Preservation Platform)

CONTROL AREA ▾ INGEST ▾ ACCESS ▾ ADMINISTRATION ▾ REPORTS ▾ MANAGEMENT ▾ HELP ▾

Create controlarea request

Please fill in the fields or use prefilled data (* indicates mandatory field)

ReqUUID: *

ReqType: *

ReqPurpose: *

User: *

ObjectIdentifierValue: *

Archive Policy ID: *

Information Class: *

DELIVERYTYPE: *

DELIVERYSPECIFICATION: *

Allow unknown filetypes:

EPP (ESSArch Preservation Platform)

CONTROL AREA ▾ INGEST ▾ ACCESS ▾ ADMINISTRATION ▾ REPORTS ▾ MANAGEMENT ▾ HELP ▾

Request to check in IP from reception

Request is in progress

EPP (ESSArch Preservation Platform) Welcome, admin. Change password / Log out

CONTROL AREA ▾ INGEST ▾ ACCESS ▾ ADMINISTRATION ▾ REPORTS ▾ MANAGEMENT ▾ HELP ▾

Request to check in IP from reception

Result:

Category: controlarea
 Label: Check In from Reception
 User: admin
 Request purpose: My purpose text
 Status: OK

Summary:

```

Found logfile: /ESSArch/data/gate/reception/93b9c63a-9507-11e6-a07b-005056982d8b/0352b7e4-94ff-11e6-af59-005056982d8b/log.xml for package: /ESSArch/data/gate/reception/93b9c63a-9507-11e6-a07b-005056982d8b/0352b7e4-94ff-11e6-af59-005056982d8b/representations/0352b7e4-94ff-11e6-af59-005056982d8b.tar
Copy package structure /ESSArch/data/gate/reception/93b9c63a-9507-11e6-a07b-005056982d8b to /ESSArch/data/epp/control/93b9c63a-9507-11e6-a07b-005056982d8b
Copy /ESSArch/data/gate/reception/93b9c63a-9507-11e6-a07b-005056982d8b/0352b7e4-94ff-11e6-af59-005056982d8b/representations/0352b7e4-94ff-11e6-af59-005056982d8b.tar to package content directory: /ESSArch/data/epp/control/93b9c63a-9507-11e6-a07b-005056982d8b/0352b7e4-94ff-11e6-af59-005056982d8b/representations
Success to get METS agents,altRecords and label from info.xml
Add altRecordID ['POLICYID', u'6e4c9b1e0bb4097aa82aff12c9fc61'] to metsfile
Add altRecordID ['INFORMATIONCLASS', u'1'] to metsfile
Add altRecordID ['DELIVERYTYPE', u'N/A'] to metsfile
Add altRecordID ['DELIVERYSPECIFICATION', u'N/A'] to metsfile
Create new PREMIS: /ESSArch/data/epp/control/93b9c63a-9507-11e6-a07b-005056982d8b/0352b7e4-94ff-11e6-af59-005056982d8b/metadata/premis.xml
Add new entry to DB for AIC_UUID: 93b9c63a-9507-11e6-a07b-005056982d8b
Add new entry to DB for IP_UUID: 0352b7e4-94ff-11e6-af59-005056982d8b
Add new entry to DB for eventIdentifierValue: 93ba4664-9507-11e6-a07b-005056982d8b
Add new entry to DB for eventIdentifierValue: 035382fa-94ff-11e6-af59-005056982d8b
    
```

CONTROL AREA -> CheckOut to Workarea

EPP (ESSArch Preservation Platform) Welcome, admin. Change password /

CONTROL AREA ▾ INGEST ▾ ACCESS ▾ ADMINISTRATION ▾ REPORTS ▾ MANAGEMENT ▾ HELP ▾

Select which information package to checkout to work area

Show entries Column visibility Search:

Identification	Archivist organization	Label	Create date	Start date	End date	Type	Generation	State	Activity
8f456056-70f3-11e6-a2ab-005056982d8b	GURS	GURS Občine Test 2SEP	2016-09-02	2016-04-11	2016-04-11	AIC			
863729c8-7b47-11e6-9554-005056982d8b	ARSO	Natura 2000 - do 2014	2016-09-15	2016-04-11	2016-04-11	AIC			
fcb7b570-7bfd-11e6-9ebb-005056982d8b	ESS	test_20160916_1	2016-09-16	2011-12-31	2012-12-29	AIC			
db616048-83e5-11e6-a759-005056982d8b	GURS3	test1	2016-09-26	2011-12-31	2012-12-29	AIC			
93b9c63a-9507-11e6-a07b-005056982d8b	ARStest	BorisTest3	2016-10-18	2016-04-11	2016-04-11	AIC			
0352b7e4-94ff-11e6-af59-005056982d8b	ARStest	BorisTest3	2016-10-18	2016-04-11	2016-04-11	SIP	IP_0	ControlArea	OK

Showing 1 to 5 of 5 entries Previous **1** Next

EPP (ESSArch Preservation Platform)

CONTROL AREA ▾ | INGEST ▾ | ACCESS ▾ | ADMINISTRATION ▾ | REPORTS ▾ | MANAGEMENT ▾ | HELP ▾

Create controlarea request

Please fill in the fields or use prefilled data (* indicates mandatory field)

ReqUUID: * ac5d151a-950d-11e6-9e8b-005056982d8b*
ReqType: * CheckOut to Workarea *
ReqPurpose: * MYControl area request *
User: * admin *
ObjectIdentifierValue: * 0352b7e4-94ff-11e6-af59-005056982d8b *
Read only access: Do not create a new IP generation

Submit →

EPP (ESSArch Preservation Platform) Welcome, admin. Change password / Log out

CONTROL AREA ▾ | INGEST ▾ | ACCESS ▾ | ADMINISTRATION ▾ | REPORTS ▾ | MANAGEMENT ▾ | HELP ▾

Request to check out IP to work area

Result:
Category: controlarea
Label: Check out to work
User: admin
Request purpose: MYControl area request text
Status: OK

Summary:
CheckOut Package: 93b9c63a-9507-11e6-a07b-005056982d8b/0352b7e4-94ff-11e6-af59-005056982d8b from source_path: /ESSArch/data/epp/control to target_path: /ESSArch/data/epp/work/admin
You have to manual delete this IP: /ESSArch/data/epp/work/admin/93b9c63a-9507-11e6-a07b-005056982d8b/0352b7e4-94ff-11e6-af59-005056982d8b from your workarea filesystem when you do not need the information any more!!
Success to create logfile: /ESSArch/data/epp/work/admin/93b9c63a-9507-11e6-a07b-005056982d8b/0352b7e4-94ff-11e6-af59-005056982d8b/log.xml

We check the folder:

Name	Size	Changed	Rights	Owner
..		18.10.2016 10:35:24	rw-rw-r-x	arch
documentation		18.10.2016 10:04:48	rw-rw-r--	arch
metadata		18.10.2016 10:32:23	rw-rw-r--	arch
representations		18.10.2016 10:04:48	rw-rw-r--	arch
schemas		18.10.2016 10:04:48	rw-rw-r--	arch
log.xml	8 KB	18.10.2016 10:35:24	rw-rw-r--	arch
mets.xml	4 KB	18.10.2016 10:32:23	rw-rw-r--	arch

CONTROL AREA -> CheckIn from Workarea

We select the package and create the request

EPP (ESSArch Preservation Platform) Welcome, admin. Change password / Log out

CONTROL AREA ▾ INGEST ▾ ACCESS ▾ ADMINISTRATION ▾ REPORTS ▾ MANAGEMENT ▾ HELP ▾

Request to check in IP from work area

Result:
Category: controlarea
Label: Check in from work
User: admin
Request purpose: Mycheckin
Status: OK

Summary:
Entry in DB for eventIdentifierValue: db61e14e-83e5-11e6-a759-005056982d8b already exist, skip to update.
Entry in DB for eventIdentifierValue: e3dad90c-83e5-11e6-a759-005056982d8b already exist, skip to update.
Entry in DB for eventIdentifierValue: 15542c9a-83e6-11e6-a370-005056982d8b already exist, skip to update.
CheckIn Package: db616048-83e5-11e6-a759-005056982d8b/ab25b67a-83e7-11e6-b6d7-005056982d8b from source_path: /ESSArch/data/epp/work/admin to target_path: /ESSArch/data/epp/control
Success to get METS agents,altRecords and label from mets.xml
Create new content METS: /ESSArch/data/epp/control/db616048-83e5-11e6-a759-005056982d8b/ab25b67a-83e7-11e6-b6d7-005056982d8b/mets.xml
Warning filetype a2ce491e-a79e-40eb-b88b-8c600d227197.zip is not recognized, setting mimetype to application/octet-stream
Create new PREMIS: /ESSArch/data/epp/control/db616048-83e5-11e6-a759-005056982d8b/ab25b67a-83e7-11e6-b6d7-005056982d8b/metadata/premis.xml
Try to remove AIC_Dir: db616048-83e5-11e6-a759-005056982d8b from source_path: /ESSArch/data/epp/work/admin

CONTROL AREA -> CheckOut to Gatearea from work

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CONTROL AREA ▾ INGEST ▾ ACCESS ▾ ADMINISTRATION ▾ REPORTS ▾ MANAGEMENT ▾ HELP ▾

Create controlarea request

Please fill in the fields or use prefilled data (* indicates mandatory field)

ReqUUID: * 77ca58f2-950e-11e6-98c7-005056982d8b *

ReqType: * CheckOut to Gatearea from WorkArea *

ReqPurpose: *

User: * admin *

Filename: *

- 93b9c63a-9507-11e6-a07b-005056982d8b/0352b7e4-94ff-11e6-af59-005056982d8b/metadata/premis.xml *
- 93b9c63a-9507-11e6-a07b-005056982d8b/0352b7e4-94ff-11e6-af59-005056982d8b/representations/0352b7e4-94ff-11e6-af59-005056982d8b.tar *
- 93b9c63a-9507-11e6-a07b-005056982d8b/0352b7e4-94ff-11e6-af59-005056982d8b/log.xml *
- 93b9c63a-9507-11e6-a07b-005056982d8b/0352b7e4-94ff-11e6-af59-005056982d8b/mets.xml *

We will not do it.

CONTROL AREA -> CheckIn from Gatearea to work

CONTROL AREA -> CheckIn from Gatearea

We will not do it:

EPP (ESSArch Preservation Platform)

CONTROL AREA ▾ INGEST ▾ ACCESS ▾ ADMINISTRATION ▾ REPORTS ▾ MANAGEMENT ▾ HELP ▾

Create controlarea request

Please fill in the fields or use prefilled data (* indicates mandatory field)

ReqUUID: * 8a638ef2-950e-11e6-9bb9-005056982d8b*

ReqType: * CheckIn from Gatearea to WorkArea *

ReqPurpose: * *

User: * admin *

Filename: * *

Submit →

CONTROL AREA -> DiffCheck

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CONTROL AREA ▾ INGEST ▾ ACCESS ▾ ADMINISTRATION ▾ REPORTS ▾ MANAGEMENT ▾ HELP ▾

Select which information package to DiffCheck

Show 10 entries

Column visibility

Search:

Identification	Archivist organization	Label	Create date	Start date	End date	Type	Generation	State	Activity
8f456056-70f3-11e6-a2ab-005056982d8b	GURS	GURS Občine Test 2SEP	2016-09-02	2016-04-11	2016-04-11	AIC			
863729c8-7b47-11e6-9554-005056982d8b	ARSO	Natura 2000 - do 2014	2016-09-15	2016-04-11	2016-04-11	AIC			
fcb7b570-7bfd-11e6-9ebb-005056982d8b	ESS	test_20160916_1	2016-09-16	2011-12-31	2012-12-29	AIC			
db616048-83e5-11e6-a759-005056982d8b	GURS3	test1	2016-09-26	2011-12-31	2012-12-29	AIC			
93b9c63a-9507-11e6-a07b-005056982d8b	ARStest	BorisTest3	2016-10-18	2016-04-11	2016-04-11	AIC			
0352b7e4-94ff-11e6-af59-005056982d8b	ARStest	BorisTest3	2016-10-18	2016-04-11	2016-04-11	SIP	IP_0	ControlArea	OK

Showing 1 to 5 of 5 entries

Previous 1 Next

EPP (ESSArch Preservation Platform)

CONTROL AREA ▾ INGEST ▾ ACCESS ▾ ADMINISTRATION ▾ REPORTS ▾ MANAGEMENT ▾ HELP ▾

Create controlarea request

Please fill in the fields or use prefilled data (* indicates mandatory field)

ReqUUID: *	b3d7c6b8-950e-11e6-9bb9-005056982d8b*
ReqType: *	DiffCheck *
ReqPurpose: *	<input type="text" value="My diffcheck"/> *
User: *	admin *
ObjectIdentifierValue: *	0352b7e4-94ff-11e6-af59-005056982d8b *

EPP (ESSArch Preservation Platform)

CONTROL AREA ▾ INGEST ▾ ACCESS ▾ ADMINISTRATION ▾ REPORTS ▾ MANAGEMENT ▾ HELP ▾

Request to Diffcheck IP

Result:

Category: controlarea
Label: Diffcheck
User: admin
Request purpose: My diffcheck
Status: OK (0)

Summary:

Success to DiffCheck object: 0352b7e4-94ff-11e6-af59-005056982d8b, ReqUUID: b3d7c6b8-950e-11e6-9bb9-005056982d8b
STATUS - confirmed:4 renamed:0 added:0 deleted:0 changed:0 permission_error:0

Detailed:

STATUS - confirmed:4 renamed:0 added:0 deleted:0 changed:0 permission_error:0

CONTROL AREA -> Preserve Information Package

Select which information package to preserve in archive

Show 10 entries

Column visibility

Search:

Identification	Archivist organization	Label	Create date	Start date	End date	Type	Generation	State	Activity
8f456056-70f3-11e6-a2ab-005056982d8b	GURS	GURS Občine Test 2SEP	2016-09-02	2016-04-11	2016-04-11	AIC			
863729c8-7b47-11e6-9554-005056982d8b	ARSO	Natura 2000 - do 2014	2016-09-15	2016-04-11	2016-04-11	AIC			
fcb7b570-7bfd-11e6-9ebb-005056982d8b	ESS	test_20160916_1	2016-09-16	2011-12-31	2012-12-29	AIC			
db616048-83e5-11e6-a759-005056982d8b	GURS3	test1	2016-09-26	2011-12-31	2012-12-29	AIC			
93b9c63a-9507-11e6-a07b-005056982d8b	ARStest	BorisTest3	2016-10-18	2016-04-11	2016-04-11	AIC			
0352b7e4-94ff-11e6-af59-005056982d8b	ARStest	BorisTest3	2016-10-18	2016-04-11	2016-04-11	SIP	IP_0	ControlArea	OK

Showing 1 to 5 of 5 entries

Previous **1** Next

EPP (ESSArch Preservation Platform) Welcome, admin. [Change password](#)

CONTROL AREA ▾ INGEST ▾ ACCESS ▾ ADMINISTRATION ▾ REPORTS ▾ MANAGEMENT ▾ HELP ▾

Create controlarea request

Please fill in the fields or use prefilled data (* indicates mandatory field)

ReqUUID: * *

ReqType: * *

ReqPurpose: * *

User: * *

ObjectIdentifierValue: * *

→

Events for IP

Event UUID	Type	Date	Outcome	Note	Agent	Generation	Linking Object ID
035382fa-94ff-11e6-af59-005056982d8b	10000	Oct. 18, 2016, 8:49 a.m.	OK	Success to create logfile	admin	IP_0	0352b7e4-94ff-11e6-af59-005056982d8b
93ba4664-9507-11e6-a07b-005056982d8b	20000	Oct. 18, 2016, 9:50 a.m.	OK	Success to create logfile	admin	IP_0	0352b7e4-94ff-11e6-af59-005056982d8b
6457d9b2-950d-11e6-9a3d-005056982d8b	30000	Oct. 18, 2016, 10:32 a.m.	OK	Success to CheckIn object: 0352b7e4-94ff-11e6-af59-005056982d8b from reception, ReqUUID: 3adc3ccc-950d-11e6-90b1-005056982d8b	admin	IP_0	0352b7e4-94ff-11e6-af59-005056982d8b
d06d04b0-950d-11e6-a370-005056982d8b	31000	Oct. 18, 2016, 10:35 a.m.	OK	Success to CheckOut object: 0352b7e4-94ff-11e6-af59-005056982d8b to workarea, ReqUUID: ac5d151a-950d-11e6-9e8b-005056982d8b	admin	IP_0	0352b7e4-94ff-11e6-af59-005056982d8b
c292298c-950e-11e6-9a3d-005056982d8b	33000	Oct. 18, 2016, 10:42 a.m.	OK	Success to DiffCheck object: 0352b7e4-94ff-11e6-af59-005056982d8b, ReqUUID: b3d7c6b8-950e-11e6-9bb9-005056982d8b, Result: STATUS - confirmed:4 renamed:0 added:0 deleted:0 changed:0 permission_error:0	admin	IP_0	0352b7e4-94ff-11e6-af59-005056982d8b

Related events for AIC

Event UUID	Type	Date	Outcome	Note	Agent	Generation	Linking Object ID
------------	------	------	---------	------	-------	------------	-------------------

Submit:

EPP (ESSArch Preservation Platform) Welcome, admin. [Change password](#)

CONTROL AREA ▾ INGEST ▾ ACCESS ▾ ADMINISTRATION ▾ REPORTS ▾ MANAGEMENT ▾ HELP ▾

Request to add information package to preservation queue initiated [Link to preservation ingest queue](#)

Result:
 Category:
 Label:
 User:
 Request purpose:
 Status:

Summary:
 Copy IP: 93b9c63a-9507-11e6-a07b-005056982d8b/0352b7e4-94ff-11e6-af59-005056982d8b from controlarea: /ESSArch/data/epp/control to ingestpath: /ESSArch/data/epp/ingest

CONTROL AREA -> Delete IP in Controlarea

CONTROL AREA -> Overview of controlarea requests

EPP (ESSArch Preservation Platform) Welcome,

CONTROL AREA ▾ INGEST ▾ ACCESS ▾ ADMINISTRATION ▾ REPORTS ▾ MANAGEMENT ▾ HELP ▾

Overview of controlarea requests

Requests from: number of days ago. [Get requests](#)

Failed requests

Request Status	Type of error	Request Result
No data available in table		

Showing 0 to 0 of 0 entries Previous Next

Pending requests

Request Status	Request Result
No data available in table	

Showing 0 to 0 of 0 entries Previous Next

Requests in progress

Request purpose	User	Request Progress
No data available in table		

Showing 0 to 0 of 0 entries Previous Next

Successful requests

Request Label	Request purpose	User	Request status	Date completed
Preserve IP	My preserve info text	admin	SUCCESS	2016-10-18
Diffcheck	My diffcheck	admin	SUCCESS	2016-10-18
Check in from work	Mycheckin	admin	SUCCESS	2016-10-18
Check out to work	MYControl area request text	admin	SUCCESS	2016-10-18

We continue with INGEST:

EPP (ESSArch Preservation Platform)

CONTROL AREA ▾ **INGEST ▾** ACCESS ▾ ADMINISTRATION ▾ REPORTS ▾ MANAGEMENT ▾ HELP ▾

Ingest information packages etc ...

Request to add information packages to the preservation queue initiated [Link to preservation ingest queue](#)

Result: [List ingest request queue](#)

Category: controlarea

INGEST -> List information packages

INGEST - List information packages

Show entries Column visibility Search:

Identification	Archivist organization	Label	Create date	Start date	End date	Type	Generation	State	Activity
No data available in table									

Showing 0 to 0 of 0 entries Previous Next

INGEST -> Create new ingest request

EPP (ESSArch Preservation Platform)

CONTROL AREA ▾ INGEST ▾ ACCESS ▾ ADMINISTRATION ▾ REPORTS ▾ MANAGEMENT ▾ HELP ▾

INGEST - Create new ingest request

Please fill in the fields or use prefilled data (* indicates mandatory field)

ReqUUID: * ec3982fe-9512-11e6-90b1-005056982d8b *

ReqType: * *

ReqPurpose: * *

User: * *

Objectidentifiervalue: * *

INGEST - List ingest request queue

ReqUUID	ReqType	ReqPurpose	User	IP (UUID)	State	Posted
ff705258-9512-11e6-9e8b-005056982d8b	Ingest request	Standard Approve	admin	My	Pending	[posted 0 minutes ago]
ff708ec6-9512-11e6-9e8b-005056982d8b	Ingest request	Standard Approve	admin	ingest	Pending	[posted 0 minutes ago]
ff70acd0-9512-11e6-9e8b-005056982d8b	Ingest request	Standard Approve	admin	request	Pending	[posted 0 minutes ago]
ff70ca26-9512-11e6-9e8b-005056982d8b	Ingest request	Standard Approve	admin	text	Pending	[posted 0 minutes ago]

We will delete some of them:

EPP (ESSArch Preservation Platform)

CONTROL AREA ▾ INGEST ▾ ACCESS ▾ ADMINISTRATION ▾ REPORTS ▾ MANAGEMENT ▾ HELP ▾

Detail information - ingest requests

[posted 1 minute ago]

Name	Value
ReqUUID	ff70acd0-9512-11e6-9e8b-005056982d8b
ReqType	Ingest request
ReqPurpose	Standard Approve
User	admin
ObjectIdentifierValue	request
Status	Pending

[Edit ingest request](#) | [Delete ingest request](#)

INGEST -> List ingest request queue

2.7.4 Access EPP

EPP (ESSArch Preservation Platform)

CONTROL AREA ▾ INGEST ▾ ACCESS ▾ ADMINISTRATION ▾ REPORTS ▾ MANAGEMENT ▾ HELP ▾

ACCESS - List information packages

Access information packages etc ..

Create new access request

List access request queue

ACCESS - List information packages

EPP (ESSArch Preservation Platform) Welcome, admin. C

CONTROL AREA ▾ INGEST ▾ ACCESS ▾ ADMINISTRATION ▾ REPORTS ▾ MANAGEMENT ▾ HELP ▾

ACCESS - List information packages

Show entries Column visibility Search:

Identification	Archivist organization	Label	Create date	Start date	End date	Type	Generation	State	Activity
fe9fb70-2e51-11e6-acc0-005056982d8b	ESS	Test 1	2016-06-09	2011-12-31	2012-12-29	AIC			
22a0f624-33a2-11e6-9f40-005056982d8b	ESS	Test 2	2016-06-16	2016-04-11	2016-04-11	AIC			
8e9561a2-7f3e-11e6-badd-005056982d8b	ESS	test20160920_1	2016-09-20	2016-04-11	2016-04-11	AIC			
93b9c63a-9507-11e6-a07b-005056982d8b	ARStest	<u>BorisTest3</u>	2016-10-18	2016-04-11	2016-04-11	AIC			
0352b7e4-94ff-11e6-af59-005056982d8b	ARStest	BorisTest3	2016-10-18	2016-04-11	2016-04-11	AIP	IP_0	Archived	OK

Showing 1 to 4 of 4 entries Previous **1** Next

ACCESS - Create new access request

EPP (ESSArch Preservation Platform)

CONTROL AREA ▾ INGEST ▾ ACCESS ▾ ADMINISTRATION ▾ REPORTS ▾ MANAGEMENT ▾ HELP ▾

ACCESS - Create new access request

Please fill in the fields or use prefilled data (* indicates mandatory field)

Available storage media: disk1_f7b9fe4c54c64e1987f6b46df91c3b2c

ReqUUID: *	8689e136-9514-11e6-9bb9-005056982d8b	*
ReqType: *	Get AIP to ControlArea ▾	*
ReqPurpose: *	Myresuest	*
User: *	admin	*
Objectidentiervalue: *	0352b7e4-94ff-11e6-af59-005056982d8b	*
StorageMediumID:		
Path: *	/ESSArch/data/epp/cont	*

Create →

EPP (ESSArch Preservation Platform)

CONTROL AREA ▾ INGEST ▾ ACCESS ▾ ADMINISTRATION ▾ REPORTS ▾ MANAGEMENT ▾ HELP ▾

Detail information - access requests

[posted 0 minutes ago]

Name	Value
ReqUUID	98d6bb70-9514-11e6-90b1-005056982d8b
ReqType	Get AIP to ControlArea
ReqPurpose	Myresuest
User	admin
ObjectIdentifierValue	0352b7e4-94ff-11e6-af59-005056982d8b
StorageMediumID	
Path	/ESSArch/data/epp/control/93b9c63a-9507-11e6-a07b-005056982d8b
Status	Pending

[Edit access request](#) | [Delete access request](#)

ACCESS - List access request queue

ACCESS - List access request queue

ReqUUID	ReqType	ReqPurpose	User	IP (UUID)	State	Posted
1edc911e-33a3-11e6-b0d4-005056982d8b	Get AIP to ControlArea	GAI2C	admin	318ec66c-33a1-11e6-952b-005056982d8b	Success	[posted 4 months ago]
ecf5d632-7f3e-11e6-b638-005056982d8b	Get AIP to ControlArea	t	admin	2f77d646-7f3e-11e6-8531-005056982d8b	Success	[posted 3 weeks, 6 days ago]
98d6bb70-9514-11e6-90b1-005056982d8b	Get AIP to ControlArea	Myresuest	admin	0352b7e4-94ff-11e6-af59-005056982d8b	Success	[posted 0 minutes ago]

Clear your successful requests

2.8 Scenario 4

Same as Scenario 2